

Predicting Student Academic Performance Using Machine Learning Models

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Full code on Github under "AI-predicting-student-performance"

Abstract:

This study uses machine learning to predict student outcomes using the UCI student database. The data includes demographic, social, and academic factors such as parental education, study time, and prior grades. These three traditional machine learning models: logistic regression, random forest, and gradient boosting were trained and then evaluated using F1 scores, accuracy and precision. Out of the three, random forest showed the highest accuracy of 91.1%, followed by gradient boosting (89.9%), and logistic regression (86.6%). Thus, these 3 models show that more complex methods such as deep learning are not required to act as a warning system for identifying at risk students and to suggest opportunities for expanding prediction accuracy through larger datasets and additional features such as attendance and extracurricular activities.

Introduction:

As artificial intelligence develops even further, it becomes an increasingly important tool in education for identifying gaps in student learning. Education is a multivariable equation affected by key factors such as study habits, family background, and past performance, all of which can affect student performance and may be overlooked by teachers. By feeding large amounts of data to machine learning models, it can help analyse this data and provide valuable predictions that assist schools in providing the necessary support for students at risk of failing. This study aims to explore whether or not machine learning models can accurately assess student outcomes using the UCI Student Performance Dataset. This will involve the comparison of three specific models: Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Gradient Boosting. It will help determine which of the three can more effectively capture the complex aspects of student learning.

Methods:

The Data Set used was the UCI Student Performance Dataset, which contains multiple variables from demographic, social, and academic variables for secondary students in Portugal.

More specifically, these variables in the database included:

- Study habits: study time.
- Family background: mother's education and father's education
- Past performance: first and second semester performances.

If a student got over 50% in their grade for their 3rd semester, they would pass. If not, they would fail.

The 3 traditional ML models that were used for testing were: logistic regression, random forest, and gradient boosting.

These models were then compared via accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. In the case of logistic regression, coefficients for each feature were used to indicate a relative importance for the factor under discussion.

While this study proves effective for predicting student performances, it is still limited by the small sample size, its restriction to only Portugal students, and the limited number of factors taken into account. All of this could be improved by using an international dataset that includes students from all over the world, considering a more diverse variety of factors.

Results:

The models each achieved the following accuracies on the test set:

Model	Accuracy
Logistic Regression	0.886
Random Forest	0.911
Gradient Boosting	0.899

- For Random Forest, it indicated that the grade for the second semester was the most important, followed by the grade for the first semester, and the other 3 factors showing similar levels.

- Logistic regression showed the same pattern as random forest, with the grade for the second semester being the most significant followed by the grade for the first semester and the other 3 factors being the least important. However, logistic regression shows that mother's education was perhaps slightly more important than study time and father's education.

- For gradient boosting, the grade for the second semester is significantly higher in importance than the other 4 factors. The other four factors show roughly the same level of importance.

Comparisons:

Among the three models, Random Forest showed the highest accuracy. Random Forest and gradient boosting were better at showing non-linear relationships, while logistic regression showed straightforward linear relationships. The 3 models conveyed that the most important of the factors were the second semester grade, followed by the first semester grade, followed by study time, followed by parents' education. These results align with traditional educational belief that past academic performance and consistency of study time influence academic achievement the most.

Conclusion:

This study shows that traditional machine learning models can effectively predict student success using easily accessible data for students. Thus, teachers can effectively use it to help struggling students. It could be improved even further using a wider range of factors including: attendance, extracurricular activities, or by adapting more complex models that use deep learning such as neural networks.

References:

1. *GritNet (2018)*
2. *Tiered Instruction Study (2025)*
3. *Neural Networks vs. Random Forest (2021)*

4. *Motivation & Family Support In Prediction (2022)*
5. *Educational Data Mining Study (2023)*
6. *UCI Student Performance Dataset*